

The Klein-Gordon Equation, $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations

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In a previous note, we argued that $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ for a nonrelativistic particle may be varied independently in T and X , where velocity = X/T . This variation indicates that energy is not kept constant. The solution $\exp(i \text{ Action}) = \exp(i .5m XX/TT)$ (for this case) leads to the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation.

In this note, we consider the free particle relativistic Lagrangian (1): $m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ where $v=X/T$. We argue that the equation describing independent fluctuations of X and T is the Klein-Gordon equation.

Non-Relativistic Case

In this case, the Lagrangian is $.5m vv$ where v is a constant which equals X/T . The action is:

$$\text{Action} = .5m XX/TT \int dt = .5m XX/T \quad ((1))$$

Then:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = \exp(i \text{ Action}) .5m XX/TT \quad (\text{which is in fact energy} * \exp(i \text{ Action})).$$

$$\text{REAL} \left[\frac{d}{dx} \right] \left[\frac{d}{dx} \right] \exp(i \text{ Action}) = [mX/T][mX/T] \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{so:}$$

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{Function}(x,t) = 1/(2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{Function}(x,t) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{as the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation.}$$

Relativistic Case

The Lagrangian in the relativistic case (1) is: $m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ and the free particle action:

$$\text{Action} = m_0 \sqrt{1- XX/TT} T \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{REAL} \left[\frac{d}{dt} \right] \left[\frac{d}{dt} \right] \exp(i \text{ Action}) = 1/[1-XX/TT] m_0 m_0 \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((5a))$$

$$\text{REAL} \left[\frac{d}{dx} \right] \left[\frac{d}{dx} \right] \exp(i \text{ Action}) = XX/TT \quad 1/[1-XX/TT] \quad m_0 m_0 \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((5b))$$

Thus:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i \text{ Action}) + \exp(i \text{ Action}) m_0 m_0 \quad ((6))$$

This is the relativistic Klein-Gordon equation i.e.

$$d/dt d/dt W(x,t) = d/dx d/dx W(x,t) + m_0 m_0 \quad ((7))$$

To see the nonrelativistic scenario emerge consider:

$$d/dt \exp(i \text{ Action}) = m_0 [XX/TT \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-XX/TT}} + \sqrt{1-XX/TT}] \quad ((8))$$

In the nonrelativistic case, $1-XX/TT$ is considered to be small i.e. XX/TT is really vv/cc where c is the speed of light, but this is not used until the last step. $((8))$ becomes:

$$i d/dt \exp(i \text{ Action}) = m_0 / \sqrt{1-XX/TT} \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((9a)) \quad (\text{no non-relativistic approx})$$

$$\text{REAL } d/dx d/dx \exp(i \text{ Action}) = [-X/T \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-vv}}] [-X/T \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-vv}}]$$

$$= m_0 m_0 XX/TT \frac{1}{[1-XX/TT]} \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((9b))$$

Considering XX/TT to be a small term (it is really divided by cc where c = speed of light), one may expand $((9a))$ and $((9b))$

$((9a))$ becomes $m_0 [1 + .5XX/TT]$ whereas $((9b))$ already has a leading $m_0 XX/TT$ small factor.

Dropping the m_0 term in $((9a))$ and comparing to $((9b))$ yields the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation i.e. i.e. $((9a)) = 1/(2m_0) ((9b))$

This is the same result which would have been obtained by immediately expanding the Lagrangian:

$$m_0 T \sqrt{1-XX/TT} = m_0 T [1 - .5XX/TT] \quad ((10))$$

$$d/dt \text{ of } \exp(i \text{ Action}) \text{ is: } [m_0 + .5m_0 XX/TT] \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((11a))$$

$$\text{REAL } 1/2m_0 d/dX d/dX \text{ of } \exp(i \text{ Action}) \text{ is: } .5 m_0 XX/TT \exp(i \text{ Action})$$

Dropping the $m_0 T$ term from $((10))$ then leads to the nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation.

Discussion

Thus, in both the nonrelativistic and relativistic cases, one may consider the propagator form $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ and vary X and T independently for the free particle. In the nonrelativistic case, the resulting equation is the Schrodinger and in the relativistic case, the Klein-Gordon equation. This may help to explain why both nonrelativistic and relativistic cases both have $\exp(i px)$ solutions (although p is nonrelativistic in one case and relativistic in the other).

Conclusion

In conclusion, in an earlier note, we argued that varying X and T independently for a free particle using $\exp(i \text{ Action})$, where $v=X/T$ in the Lagrangian, leads to a fluctuation equation in the form of the Schrodinger equation. This type of fluctuation means one considers different velocity and hence different energy values. Thus, $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ represents different energies i.e. may be expanded in terms of various energy eigenstates of the Schrodinger equation. Interestingly, the Schrodinger equation also admits specific average energy solutions e.g. $\exp(ipx)$.

In this note, we carry these ideas over to the relativistic case and find the same fluctuations lead to the Klein-Gordon equation. We also see that the Schrodinger nonrelativistic case follows from the relativistic one. Thus, independent fluctuations in X and T for $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ where $\text{Action} = \text{Integral } dt \text{ Lagrangian}$ lead to both the nonrelativistic and relativistic quantum mechanical equations (i.e. the Schrodinger and Klein-Gordon equations).

References

1. Redmount, I. and Suen, W. Path Integration in Relativistic Quantum Mechanics (1992)
<https://arxiv.org/abs/gr-qc/9210019v1>